

1 RESEARCH PAPER

2 **Gypsum-exclusive plants accumulate more leaf S than non-exclusive species both in and**
3 **off gypsum**

4 Andreu Cera^{1,2*}, Gabriel Montserrat-Martí³, Juan Pedro Ferrio^{4,5}, Rebecca E. Drenovsky⁶,
5 Sara Palacio¹

6 ¹ Departamento Biodiversidad y Restauración, Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología, Consejo
7 Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Avenida Nuestra Señora de la Victoria, 16, Jaca, ES-
8 22700, Spain

9 ² Departament de Biologia Evolutiva, Ecologia i Ciències Ambientals (BEECA), Secció de
10 Botànica i Micologia, Facultat de Biologia, Universitat de Barcelona, Diagonal, 643,
11 Barcelona, ES-08028, Spain

12 ³ Departamento Biodiversidad y Restauración, Instituto Pirenaico de Ecología, Consejo
13 Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Avda. Montañana 1070C, Zaragoza, ES-50820, Spain

14 ⁴ Aragon Agency for Research and Development (ARAID), Zaragoza, Spain

15 ⁵ Unidad de Recursos Forestales, Centro de Investigación y Tecnología Agroalimentaria de
16 Aragón (CITA). Avda. Montañana 930, Zaragoza, ES-50059, Spain

17 ⁶ Biology Department, John Carroll University, John Carroll Blvd., University Heights, Ohio
18 44118, USA

19 Gypsophiles accumulate more leaf S than gypsumvags both in and off gypsum

20 * Corresponding author: andreucera@outlook.com

21

1 **Abstract**

2 Gypsum-exclusive species (gypsophiles), are restricted to gypseous soils in natural
3 environments. However, it is unclear why gypsophiles display greater affinity to gypseous
4 soils than other soils. These plants are edaphic endemics, growing in alkaline soils with high
5 Ca and S. Gypsophiles tend to show higher foliar Ca and S, lower K and, sometimes, higher
6 Mg than non-exclusive gypsum species, named gypsovags. Our aim was to test if the unique
7 leaf elemental signature of gypsophiles could be the result of special nutritional requirements
8 linked to their specificity to gypseous soils. These nutritional requirements could hamper the
9 completion of their life cycle and growth in other soil types. To test this hypothesis, we
10 cultivated five gypsophiles and five gypsovags dominant in Spanish gypsum outcrops on
11 gypseous and calcareous (non-gypseous) field soil for 29 months. We regularly measured
12 growth and phenology, and differences in leaf traits, final biomass, individual seed mass, seed
13 viability, photosynthetic assimilation and leaf elemental composition. We found all the
14 gypsophiles studied were able to complete their life cycle in non-gypseous soil, producing
15 viable seeds, attaining greater biomass and displaying higher photosynthetic assimilation rates
16 than in gypseous soil. The leaf elemental composition of some species (both gypsophiles and
17 gypsovags) shifted depending on soil, although none of them showed leaf deficiency
18 symptoms. Regardless of soil type, gypsophiles had higher leaf S, Mg, Fe, Al, Na, Mn, Cr and
19 lower K than gypsovags. Consequently, gypsophiles have a unique leaf chemical signature
20 compared to gypsovags of the same family, particularly due to their high leaf S regardless of
21 soil conditions. However, these nutrient requirements are not sufficient to explain why
22 gypsophiles are restricted to gypsum soil in natural conditions.

23 **Key words**

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- 1 gypsophile, semiarid, thiophores, leaf chemical signature, nutrient, phenology, edaphism,
- 2 gypsum
- 3

1 **1. Introduction**

2 The effect of soil on plant performance and distribution has been studied by ecologists
3 and botanists for decades, particularly in relation to the restriction of plants to certain types of
4 soils with special physicochemical features. For example, serpentines and saline soils are
5 special substrates that support singular floras (Mota *et al.*, 2017) composed of species that
6 tolerate the physicochemical challenges imposed by them (Kazakou *et al.*, 2008, Munns and
7 Tester, 2008).

8 Gypseous soils are also atypical substrates. These soils have high gypsum content
9 (Casby-Horton *et al.*, 2015) and normally develop in arid or semiarid environments, limiting
10 plant life (Palacio *et al.*, 2017). High gypsum content in soil impacts the physical and
11 chemical properties of soils and their functions (Herrero and Porta, 2000). The moderate
12 solubility of gypsum (about 2.4 g l⁻¹) leads to highly dynamic soil environments, with
13 dissolution-precipitation sequences altering physical properties (Casby-Horton *et al.*, 2015).
14 Although the solubility of gypsum does not produce osmotic or ion-toxic stress for plants
15 (Casby-Horton *et al.*, 2015), the chemical conditions of gypseous soils influence plant
16 nutrition (Boukhris and Loissant, 1972; Palacio *et al.*, 2007; Salmerón-Sánchez *et al.*, 2014),
17 ultimately limiting growth (FAO, 1990).

18 Plants living on gypseous soils have to cope with alkaline soils saturated in calcium,
19 sulphate and magnesium ions, and reduced in N, P and K availability (Moore *et al.*, 2014).
20 Gypseous soils have low nutrient retention (Casby-Horton *et al.*, 2015) and high Ca cation
21 activity due to the solubility of gypsum (FAO, 1990). The combination of high Ca, jointly
22 with high sulphate, alters plant metabolism (Meyer, 1980) and decreases the availability and
23 uptake of macronutrients like K and P (Stout *et al.*, 1951; FAO, 1990). To overcome these

1 chemical restrictions, plants growing on gypseous soils may have developed special
2 mechanisms and strategies (Moore *et al.*, 2014).

3 Species that thrive on special soils generally show different ecological amplitudes,
4 ranging from tolerant species with a broad distribution, to highly specialized edaphic
5 endemics restricted to them (Kruckeberg and Rabinowitz, 1985). In the case of gypseous
6 soils, Meyer (1986) described mainly two types of plants living on gypsum, depending on
7 their affinity to this substrate: 1) gypsovags, species with wide ecological amplitude, which
8 can grow both on and off gypseous soils; and 2) gypsophiles, edaphic endemics restricted to
9 gypseous soils. Two types of gypsophiles have been further described (Palacio *et al.*, 2007):
10 widely distributed gypsophiles (hereafter, wide gypsophiles) considered as gypsum specialists
11 (*sensu* Gankin and Major, 1964), and narrowly distributed gypsophiles, which, similar to
12 gypsovags, would fit the refuge model, being stress tolerant species not specifically adapted
13 to gypseous soils. Gypsovags seem to be stress tolerant plants that may display different
14 mechanisms to cope with the limitations imposed by gypsum (Bolukbasi *et al.*, 2016).
15 Gypsophiles are usually restricted to gypseous soils (Mota *et al.*, 2011), and their individual
16 fitness may be compromised in non-gypseous soils (Ballesteros *et al.*, 2014). However, it is
17 unclear why gypsophiles display greater affinity to gypseous soils than other soil types.

18 Edaphic endemics often have substrate-specific physiological mechanisms or strategies
19 to cope with the harsh conditions of special substrates (Mota *et al.*, 2017). In soils with
20 atypical chemical composition, the mineral nutrition of plants has been crucial to explain
21 plant restriction or growth limitation (Rorison, 1960). The concentration of elements in leaves
22 (hereafter, leaf elemental composition) is used to understand plant mineral nutrition, since it
23 links plant function (Aerts and Chapin, 1999) and soil chemistry. For example, halophytes
24 require high concentrations of NaCl (100–200 mM) for optimal growth (Flowers *et al.*, 1977)

1 and show high leaf Na, Mg and low Ca, K, as compared to co-occurring non-specialized
2 species (Matinzadeh *et al.*, 2019). In serpentine soils, edaphic endemics maintain high leaf
3 Ca:Mg molar ratios (O'Dell *et al.*, 2006), indicating that they have a high selectivity for Ca at
4 the root surface, maintaining sufficient Ca uptake despite a very low soil Ca:Mg ratio
5 (Kazakou *et al.*, 2008). While, consistent chemical patterns have been found in wide
6 gypsophiles, who display a common leaf elemental composition similar to that of the
7 gypseous soils in which they grow (Duvigneaud and Denaeyer-De Smet, 1968).

8 Wide gypsophiles tend to have higher foliar S and Ca, lower K and, sometimes, higher
9 foliar Mg as compared to co-existing gypsovags (Duvigneaud and Denaeyer- De Smet, 1968;
10 Boukhris and Loissant 1970, 1972, 1975; Alvarado, 1995; Palacio *et al.*, 2007; Muller *et al.*,
11 2017). This unique leaf chemical composition was observed despite phylogenetic constraints
12 in gypsophilic species from the Chihuahuan Desert (Muller *et al.*, 2017). However, the
13 ecological or adaptive implications of the atypical chemical composition of wide gypsophiles
14 remain unexplored. It has been suggested that the leaf elemental composition of wide
15 gypsophiles could be a nutritional requirement to complete their life cycle and support growth
16 or could confer some form of protection from competition or disturbances (Meyer, 1980).
17 However, no previous studies have evaluated the nutrient composition of wide gypsophiles
18 growing on non-gypseous soils.

19 Our aim was to test if wide gypsophiles are restricted to gypseous soils because they are
20 not able to complete their life cycle off gypsum. We focused only on wide gypsophiles
21 (hereafter, gypsophiles), since narrowly distributed gypsophiles are a less distinctive group.
22 We also wanted to explore the extent to which the atypical chemical composition of
23 gypsophiles is linked to chemical conditions of the substrate. To this end, we cultivated five
24 widespread Iberian gypsophiles and five co-occurring gypsovags (some of them closely

1 related phylogenetically) in gypsum and calcareous (non-gypseous) soils. The selection of
2 calcareous soil as the non-gypsum treatment stemmed from the fact that gypsum outcrops are
3 frequently intermingled with alternating layers of marls, limestone and clays (Quirantes,
4 1978). Consequently, calcareous soils are the most readily available non-gypsum alternative
5 for plants growing on gypseous soils in the wild, showing similar physicochemical features
6 including similar Ca content and differing mainly in the higher S content of gypseous soils
7 (FAO, 1990). We analysed plant survival and fitness and measured leaf elemental
8 composition as a tool to understand plant mineral nutrition and its relationship with soil
9 chemical features. We hypothesized that: 1) Gypsophiles would have lower growth and
10 fitness in non-gypseous soils than in gypseous soils, in accordance with Ballesteros *et al.*
11 (2014); 2) Gypsophiles would have substrate-specific physiological mechanisms or strategies
12 linked with chemical features of gypseous soils (i.e., nutritional requirements), and as a result,
13 they would accumulate higher S and Mg concentrations than gypsovags, irrespective of the
14 substrate. However, such concentrations would be lower on calcareous (non-gypseous) than
15 on gypseous soil, owing to the lower S and Mg availability in the former.

16

17 **2. Material and Methods**

18 *2.1. Study species*

19 The selected species included a suite of five dominant gypsophile and gypsovag sub-
20 shrubs from gypsum environments in northeastern Spain (Table 1). Gypsophile species
21 included *Gypsophila struthium* subsp. *hispanica* (Willk.) G.López., *Herniaria fruticosa* L.,
22 *Helianthemum squamatum* Pers., *Lepidium subulatum* L., *Ononis tridentata* L.; and gypsovag
23 species included *Boleum asperum* Desv., *Helianthemum syriacum* (Jacq.) Dum.Cours., *Linum*
24 *suffruticosum* DC., *Matthiola fruticulosa* (L.) Maire and *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. All the

1 gypsophile species included in the study show high affinity for gypseous soils (Mota *et*
2 *al.*,2011) and are widely distributed within the Iberian Peninsula (Palacio *et al.*,2007).

3

4 2.2. Soil collection and analyses

5 Gypseous soil was collected from a gypsum outcrop in the Middle Ebro Basin
6 (Villamayor del Gállego, Zaragoza, Spain, 41°41'44.5" N, 0°44'26.7" W) and calcareous soil
7 (non-gypseous, hereafter calcareous) was collected from the Iberian System (Ricla, Zaragoza,
8 Spain, 41°30'45.8"N, 1°26'47.8"W). Soil was collected by removing O horizons in
9 unfertilized areas, sieved to 1 cm, and then thoroughly mixed and used to fill pots. Physical
10 and chemical properties were analysed from five replicates per experimental soil type (Table
11 A.1).

12 Soils were air dried for 2 months prior to physical and chemical analyses and
13 subsequently divided into two subsamples: one to be sieved to pass a 2 mm sieve, and the
14 other to remain non-sieved. Sieved soils were used to measure the following variables:
15 gypsum content, measured according to Artieda *et al.* (2006); carbonate content determined
16 by Bernard calcimetry; soil texture, estimated with a particle laser analyser (Mastersizer 2000
17 Hydro G, Malvern, UK); and soil pH and conductivity, measured with a pH/conductivity
18 meter (Orio StarA215, Thermo Scientific, Waltham-MA, USA) by diluting samples with
19 distilled water to 1:2.5 (w/v) to measure pH and then 1:5 (w/v) to measure conductivity). A
20 subsample of each sieved soil was finely ground using a ball mill (Retsch MM200, Restch
21 GmbH, Haan, Germany) and subsequently used to analyse elemental concentrations. N and C
22 concentrations were measured with an elemental analyzer (TruSpec CN, LECO, St. Joseph-
23 MI, USA), whereas the elemental composition of Al, As, Ca, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, K, Li,
24 Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, Ni, P, Pb, S, Se, Si, Ti, V, Zn was measured by extracting samples with

1 HNO₃-H₂O₂ (9:3) by microwave acid digestion (Speed Ave MWS-3⁺, BERGHOF, Eningen,
2 Germany), followed by inductively coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (Varian
3 ICP 720-ES, Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara-CA, USA). All elemental analyses were
4 performed by EEZ-CSIC Analytical Services.

5

6 *2.3. Experimental design*

7 For each species, seeds were collected from several individuals within the same
8 population (Table 1). In April 2016, seeds were germinated in nursery trays with 0.06 L cells
9 filled with a one-part gravel in the bottom of the cell and four-parts field soil on top of it. Half
10 of the trays had calcareous soil and the other half had gypseous soil (see Table A.1, A.2, for
11 soil features). In November 2016, plants with high root volume (*G. hispanica*, *R. officinalis*
12 and *O. tridentata*) and plants with shallow roots (the rest of species) were transplanted into 7
13 L and 5.6 L square pots, respectively. Five months after transplantation, pots were thinned to
14 one plant per pot, with ten replicates per species and soil treatment. All plants were kept well-
15 watered throughout the experiment and regularly de-weeded by hand, removing any potential
16 competition and drought stress. Each year, throughout the duration of the experiment, plants
17 were housed in a greenhouse from November to March to avoid freezing damage. Five
18 replicates per species and soil treatment were harvested in September 2019, 29 months after
19 sowing.

20

21 *2.4. Phenological patterns and growth*

22 Phenological patterns were recorded for each plant every two weeks between 29
23 November 2017 and 7 Sept. 2019. Five phenophases were considered (adapted from
24 Montserrat-Martí *et al.*, 2009): plant vegetative growth, flower bud formation, flowering, fruit

1 set and leaf shedding. The incidence of each phenophase was estimated in the canopy of each
2 individual as the percentage of stems displaying it. Canopy height, maximum shoot length
3 (measured from the base of plant to the distant most leaf, hereafter canopy length), and the
4 maximum and their perpendicular canopy diameters were measured monthly using a metallic
5 millimetre straightedge. Mature fruits were collected at seeding and stored in a dry location at
6 room temperature until seed viability tests.

7

8 *2.5. Leaf gas exchange, plant biomass, functional traits and seed traits*

9 Leaf gas exchange, including photosynthetic assimilation and stomatal conductance,
10 were measured with a Portable Photosynthesis System coupled with a Chlorophyll
11 Fluorescence Module (CIRAS-2, PP Systems, Amesbury-MA, USA), a LED light unit on the
12 leaf cuvette (PLC6 U), and a circular bead plate of 18 mm diameter. Three plants of each soil
13 treatment and species were measured after 9 am and before 1 pm on 11 July 2017, except for
14 *M. fruticulosa* and *B. asperum*, which did not have enough green leaves for assessment.

15 At harvest in September 2019, plants were lifted from their pots and rinsed with tap
16 water to remove soil. Plants were separated into green leaves, stems, fine roots (diameter < 2
17 mm), coarse roots (rest of roots), and seeds (if available). All plant fractions were
18 subsequently dried to a constant weight at 50 °C and weighed in a precision scale (42 g /
19 0.00001 g, MS105DU, Mettler Toledo, Columbus-OH, USA).

20 Specific leaf area (SLA) was measured as the one-sided area of a fresh leaf divided by
21 its oven-dry mass. Leaf dry matter content (LDMC) was measured as the oven-dry mass (mg)
22 of a leaf, divided by its water-saturated fresh mass (g), expressed in mg g⁻¹ (Pérez-
23 Harguindeguy *et al.*, 2013). To measure leaf area, images of leaves were captured with a Dino-
24 Lite Digital Microscope (AnMo Electronics, Taiwan) and processed with ImageJ (National

1 Institutes of Health, Bethesda-MD, USA). SLA and LDMC were calculated for the final
2 harvest from among 4-10 individual leaves of each plant with petioles included.

3 Individual seed mass was weighed on a precision scale (42 g / 0.00001 g, MS105DU,
4 Mettler Toledo, Columbus-OH, USA) as total seed weight divided by number of seeds ($N =$
5 20). Seed viability was assessed by monitoring the emergence of 20 seeds per species over 30
6 days. Seeds were sown on filter paper inside Petri dishes, kept well-watered with distilled
7 water, and placed in a growth chamber (ASL Aparatos Científicos, Madrid, Spain) with 16
8 hours of light (flux= 1743-1900 lm, CCT = 4000-6500 K) at 25 °C and 8 hours of darkness at
9 15 °C.

10

11 2.6. Leaf chemical analyses

12 To assess leaf elemental composition, we collected leaf tissue from three to five
13 individuals per species and soil type during two sampling periods: October 2017 and
14 September-November 2018; different replicates were assessed at the two sampling periods.
15 Leaves were dried to a constant weight at 50 °C and subsequently finely ground using a ball
16 mill (Retsch MM200, Restch GmbH, Haan, Germany). N and C concentrations were analysed
17 with an elemental analyzer (TruSpec CN, LECO, St. Joseph-MI, USA). The elemental
18 composition of Al, As, Ca, Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, K, Li, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, Ni, P, Pb, S, Se,
19 Si, Ti, V, Zn was measured by extracting samples with HNO₃-H₂O₂ (8:2) by microwave acid
20 digestion (Speed Ave MWS-3⁺, BERGHOF, Eningen, Germany), followed by inductively
21 coupled plasma-optical emission spectrometry (Varian ICP 720-ES, Agilent Technologies,
22 Santa Clara-CA, USA). All elemental analyses were performed by EEZ-CSIC Analytical
23 Services. Only elements with values above 0.025 ppm (the detection limit of the ICP-OES
24 spectrometer) were included in the statistical analyses.

1

2

3 2.7. Calculations and statistics

4 All statistical analyses were run in R 3.6.0 (R Core Team, 2020).

5 To model the gradualness of growth and flowering patterns, changes in canopy length
6 and in the percentage of shoots bearing flowers within the canopy over time were fitted to a
7 Boltzmann sigmoid regression (Self-Starting Nls Four-Parameter Logistic Model function on
8 R). In this analysis, the scale parameter indicates the steepness of the curve and, consequently,
9 the gradualness of the change in growth or flowering (Palacio *et al.*, 2013). Shoot growth rate
10 (L -day, mm day^{-1}) was calculated as the difference in canopy length between two consecutive
11 monthly measurements divided by the number of days elapsed between both measurements.
12 The maximum value of shoot growth rate, the day with the maximum shoot growth rate, the
13 day of first flowering, the day with the maximum percentage of stems with flowers (day of
14 maximum flowering), and the maximum flowering (maximum percentage of stems with
15 flowers) were selected as variables to study changes in phenological patterns. Water use
16 efficiency (WUE) was calculated by dividing the photosynthetic assimilation (A) by stomatal
17 conductance (g_s) (Pérez-Harguindeguy *et al.*, 2013).

18 Differences between soils and gypsum affinity plant types (i.e. gypsophiles and
19 gypsovags) for the variables canopy length and canopy area at harvest, gradualness of shoot
20 growth (slope of the Boltzmann curve), maximum shoot growth rate, day of maximum shoot
21 growth rate, photosynthetic assimilation (A), stomatal conductance (g_s), transpiration (E),
22 instantaneous Water Use Efficiency (WUE), day of first flowering, day of maximum
23 flowering, maximum percentage of flowering, individual seed mass, total biomass, root:shoot
24 ratio and for each elemental concentration were analysed by generalized linear mixed models

1 (hereafter GLMM) with “soil” (gypseous / calcareous) and “gypsum affinity” (gypsophile /
2 gypsovag) as fixed factors and “species” as a random factor. Species was included as a
3 random factor to account for species-specific effects and avoid biases related to species
4 selection. In the case of elemental concentrations, we also added taxonomic “family”, and
5 “species” nested within “family” and “year” as random factors to avoid biases related to
6 phylogenetic effects on elemental concentration (Neugebauer *et al.*, 2018) or different
7 sampling dates. Analyses were assessed with function *glmm* on R (*lme4* package version 1.1-
8 15 in R, Bates *et al.*, 2007). The models were fitted to a Gamma distribution when there was
9 not a normal distribution of residuals since, in most cases, data had a constant coefficient of
10 variation and variances increased with means (McCullagh and Nelder, 1989). Model link
11 functions of the Gamma distribution were selected according to the lower AIC criterion and
12 included in each table as sub-indexes. Similarly, differences between soil types within each
13 gypsum affinity class and differences between soil types within each species were assessed by
14 GLMM.

15 Principal Component Analysis (PCA, *vegan* package version 2.4-6 in R, Oksanen *et*
16 *al.*, 2007, and *ggplot2* package in R, Wickham, 2016) was used to visualize relationships
17 among elemental concentrations and taxa. We used elements with concentrations above the
18 detection limit of the ICP-OES spectrometer and samples for which we also had N and C
19 concentration data ($N = 182$). All elemental data were transformed to Center Log-Ratio
20 coordinates (Aitchison, 1982) using CoDaPack (Comas-Cufí and Thió-Henestrosa, 2011), to
21 maintain relationships between elements regardless of the concentration, which allows
22 studying joint patterns among elements (Soriano-Disla *et al.*, 2013, Prater *et al.*, 2019).
23 Redundancy Analysis (RDA, *vegan* package version 2.4-6 in R, Oksanen *et al.*, 2007) was

1 performed with the same data set as the PCA, including “soil” (gypseous / calcareous) and
2 “gypsum affinity” (gypsophile / gypsovag) as fixed factors.

3 Differences in nutrient composition between soils and species were assessed using
4 non-parametric contrasts based on distance (Adonis function on *vegan* package version 2.4-6
5 in R, Oksanen *et al.*, 2007) with “soil” (gypseous / calcareous) and “species” as fixed factors
6 and using the Euclidean as distance from Center Log-ratio coordinates. Significant
7 interactions between soil and species on nutrient composition was analysed by multilevel
8 pairwise comparisons with “interaction” as a fixed factor (*pairwiseAdonis* package version
9 0.3 in R, Martinez-Arbizu, 2019).

10 A heat map (*ggplot2* package in R, Wickham, 2016) was used to visualize the distances
11 among soils and species jointly with a cladogram from an adapted phylogenetic tree.
12 Distances were calculated using Euclidean as distance from Center Log-Ratio coordinates
13 (*vegdist* function on *vegan* package version 2.4-6 in R, Oksanen *et al.*, 2007). Distances
14 among branches of the cladogram were extracted from Tree of Life Web Project (Maddison
15 and Schulz, 2007).

16

17 **3. Results**

18 *3.1. Life cycle, growth and phenology*

19 Contrary to our expectations, gypsophile species had similar growth, and similar
20 maximum percentage of stems with flowers and individual seed mass, in both substrates
21 (Table 2, and see F-ratios of GLMMs on Tables A.3, A.4). Also, they produced fruits which
22 rendered viable seeds. Similarly, and in agreement with our expectations, gypsovags
23 completed their life cycle in both soil types, except for *R. officinalis*, which did not produce
24 fruits in either substrate. Gypsovags had similar growth and lower individual seed mass in

1 gypseous than calcareous soils, and a similar maximum percentage of stems with flowers in
2 both substrates ($P < 0.05$).

3 Gypsophiles and gypsovags differed in plant size, leaf traits, growth, and phenology
4 (Table 2). Regardless of the soil type, gypsophiles had larger canopy areas than gypsovags,
5 1.4-fold lower Root:Shoot ratios and 1.5 fold lower LDMC ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore, the
6 timing of phenological events was delayed in gypsophiles as compared to gypsovags,
7 independent of soil type. Gypsophiles attained maximal shoot growth rate 31 days later on
8 average than gypsovags in both soil types ($P < 0.05$, Figure 1a). Gypsophiles also initiated
9 flowering and reached maximal bloom almost two months later than gypsovags on average (P
10 < 0.05 for both traits, Figure 1b). Soil type had an effect on the flowering phenology of
11 gypsovags: plants grown on calcareous soil initiated flowering earlier than those grown on
12 gypsum ($P < 0.05$).

13 Regardless of the species or gypsum affinity, plants grown in calcareous soil had larger
14 canopy area and total biomass ($P < 0.05$, Table 2). They also had 1.2-fold higher
15 photosynthetic assimilation, 1.2-fold higher SLA, and started flowering ten days earlier on
16 average than plants grown on gypseous soil ($P < 0.05$, Table 2). Considering each gypsum
17 affinity separately, gypsophiles grown in calcareous soil had larger canopy area and higher
18 SLA than those grown on gypsum ($P < 0.05$, Table 2). Gypsophiles reached their maximal
19 shoot growth rate 27 days later, on average ($P < 0.05$), when growing on calcareous vs.
20 gypseous soil. Gypsovags grown in calcareous soil had higher total biomass and leaf N at
21 harvest and lower individual seed mass than those grown on gypsum ($P < 0.05$). Gypsovags
22 also initiated flowering later on gypsum than calcareous soil ($P < 0.05$, Table 2).

23

24 *3.2. Leaf elemental composition*

1 Gypsophiles had a different leaf elemental composition compared to gypsovags that was
2 independent of soil type ($P < 0.05$, Table 3), and these differences were maintained in both
3 samplings (data not shown). Gypsophiles and gypsovags shifted their leaf elemental
4 composition based on soil type ($P < 0.05$, Table 3). As indicated by the PCA biplot, plant leaf
5 elemental composition was more strongly influenced by phylogenetic relationships than by
6 soil type, with species of the same family plotting close to each other, regardless of soil type
7 (Figure 2). The biplot of the first and second PCA axes indicated that gypsophiles showed a
8 unique leaf elemental composition compared to gypsovags, irrespectively of the substrate.
9 Gypsophiles growing on both soil types were located in the upper quadrants and associated
10 with the vectors for S, Cu, Mg, Ti, Al, Fe, Mn. This pattern indicates they showed higher
11 concentrations of these elements, regardless of soil type. In contrast, gypsovags were located
12 in the bottom left quadrant, aligned with higher K, P, Zn and N concentrations. Furthermore,
13 the biplot of first and second or second and third PCA axes (Figure 2, and Figure B.1)
14 indicated that plants from different soil type were distributed along the second component.
15 Plants grown in gypseous soils had more positive values along the second component than
16 those grown in calcareous soils, and S vectors had positive values and K and P vectors had
17 negative values. This pattern indicates plants grown on gypsum had high leaf S and low leaf
18 K and P. In accordance with the PCA results, gypsum affinity and soil types were associated
19 with different leaf elemental compositions based on the RDA analysis (F -ratio = 32.11 for
20 gypsum affinity, $P < 0.05$; F -ratio = 8.72, $P < 0.05$, for soil type, respectively, $TVE = 18.8\%$
21 for RDA model, Figure B.2).

22 Assessing each element separately, gypsophiles had higher leaf Mg, S, Fe, Al, Na, Mn,
23 Cu than gypsovags and lower K concentrations ($P < 0.05$, Table 4, see F -ratios of GLMMs on
24 Tables A.5, A.6). Particularly large differences were observed for S and Mg. Leaf S of

1 gypsophiles was triple that of gypsovags, and leaf Mg was 2.4-fold greater in gypsophiles
2 than gypsovags. The leaf S concentration of gypsovags increased from 5.9 mg·g⁻¹ in
3 calcareous soil to 7.7 mg·g⁻¹ in gypsum ($P < 0.05$), whereas S concentrations in gypsophiles
4 shifted from 15.6 mg·g⁻¹ in calcareous soil to 24.4 mg·g⁻¹ in gypsum soil ($P < 0.05$). In
5 contrast, leaf Mg of gypsovags and gypsophiles did not differ between soil types. Leaf Ca was
6 similar between gypsophiles and gypsovags on gypsum, but gypsophiles had almost twice the
7 leaf Ca concentrations of gypsovags when growing on calcareous soil ($P < 0.05$). Gypsovags
8 increased Ca concentrations up to 1.15-fold when growing on gypsum ($P < 0.05$), whereas
9 gypsophiles had similar Ca concentrations on both substrates. For leaf Cr and Mo,
10 gypsophiles had greater concentrations when grown on gypseous soil ($P < 0.05$), whereas
11 gypsovags had similar concentrations in both soils. In general, plants grown on calcareous
12 soil had higher P, K and C and lower S, Mo, Li, Mn, Cu and Mg, than those cultivated on
13 gypseous soils ($P < 0.05$).

14 Despite these general trends, some species-specific trends were observed. In
15 accordance with the PCA results, the gypsophile *H. fruticosa* was closer to gypsovags than
16 gypsophiles in both soils, whereas the opposite was true for the gypsovag *H. syriacum* (Figure
17 2, and Figure B.2). Furthermore, some species of gypsophiles and gypsovags shifted their leaf
18 elemental composition between soil types ($P < 0.05$, Table A.7), as observed in distance
19 biplots (Figures 2 and B.1) or the heatmap of distances (Figure B.3). Shifts in leaf elemental
20 composition were mainly related to leaf S, K, P, regardless of gypsum affinity (Tables A.8
21 and A.9).

22

23 4. Discussion

1 In contrast to our expectations, gypsophiles had equal or better growth and fitness when
2 growing in calcareous soils. Gypsovags also had similar or higher growth and fitness in
3 calcareous soil than gypseous soil, which is not surprising owing to their widespread
4 occurrence on both substrates. In support of our second hypothesis, gypsophiles showed
5 higher S and Mg concentrations than gypsovags irrespective of the soil type. However, both
6 groups of plants shifted their leaf elemental composition according to soil nutrient availability
7 and had higher leaf S and Mg when growing on gypseous soils. Despite these general trends,
8 species-specific responses were observed within gypsum affinities.

9

10 *4.1. Gypsophiles completed their life cycle on calcareous soil, being similarly or even*
11 *more productive than on gypseous soil*

12 Gypsum-exclusive species are restricted to gypseous soils in natural environments.
13 However, we observed that gypsophiles were able to complete their life cycle, producing
14 viable seeds in calcareous soils in the greenhouse. This result demonstrates that soil chemistry
15 alone is not a factor preventing the occurrence of gypsophiles off of gypseous soils. This
16 result is supported by field observations in Spain indicating that, even though gypsophiles are
17 far more frequently found on gypseous soils, they are sometimes also found naturally off
18 gypseous soils (Mota *et al.*, 2011, Luzuriaga *et al.*, 2015). Nevertheless, it is unclear if the few
19 gypsophile individuals found growing off gypseous soils in nature could complete their life
20 cycle, producing viable seeds and recruiting new individuals, since most data were
21 observations of presence / absence. In any case, care should be taken when extrapolating
22 results from experimental studies to natural conditions (Wenk and Dawson, 2007). Our
23 experiment involved regular de-weeding and watering, removing any potential competition
24 from neighbouring plants or water stress, conditions that are far from those in natural

1 environments. The combination of different stress factors (plant competition, drought and
2 altered soil chemistry) could be the underlying mechanism explaining gypsophile restriction
3 to gypseous soils, rather than soil chemistry alone, as demonstrated by our experiment.
4 Further experiments on natural gypseous and calcareous soils testing for the combined effects
5 of soil chemistry plus plant competition and water availability are needed to shed light on
6 these issues.

7 In contrast to our first hypothesis, some gypsophiles were more productive on
8 calcareous than on gypseous soil, showing higher photosynthetic assimilation rates, higher
9 SLA and larger biomass. Ballesteros *et al.* (2014) found poorer plant performance on marls
10 than gypseous soils. Our calcareous soil had higher pH, N, P and K and lower conductivity, S
11 and Mg concentrations, indicating better conditions than gypseous soil for standard plant
12 growth. Both gypsum affinity groups showed a delay in the initiation of flowering when
13 growing on gypseous soils, probably due to the more stressful conditions of gypsum for plant
14 growth. However, we observed that gypsophiles showed a consistent phenological delay
15 compared to gypsovags. Such a phenological delay has been described in the literature
16 (Escudero *et al.*, 2014), although the ecological and adaptive factors behind it remain
17 unexplored. Furthermore, gypsophiles did not show any leaf deficiency symptoms and had
18 similar maximum flower production and individual seed mass in both soils, similar to
19 gypsovags. Similarly, Heiden *et al.*, (unpubl. res.) observed that gypsophiles had low
20 germination in acidic soils but germinated equally well on alkaline calcareous and gypseous
21 soils. Consequently, gypsophiles seem to require soils with high pH and high Ca availability
22 to germinate and complete their life cycle, but do not have a requirement for high S or
23 gypsum to grow and complete their life cycle under experimental conditions.

24

1 4.2. *Gypsophiles* displayed higher leaf S and Mg and lower leaf K than gypsovags both
2 *in and off gypsum*

3 In accordance with our second hypothesis, gypsophiles had higher leaf S and Mg and
4 lower K concentrations than gypsovags in both soil types. This pattern indicates a high
5 preference of gypsophiles for these two elements, in accordance with previous studies of
6 plants growing on gypseous soils, where the S and Mg concentrations of gypsophiles tended
7 to be higher than those of gypsovags (Alvarado, 1995, Palacio *et al.*, 2007, Muller *et al.*,
8 2017).

9 The ability of gypsophiles to accumulate S was remarkable, reaching S foliar
10 concentrations between $15 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and $25 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, one order of magnitude higher than standard
11 foliar S concentrations of non S-deprived plants (Kalra, 1997). Such high S-accumulation was
12 maintained even when grown in calcareous soil, which had 55-fold less S than the gypseous
13 soil. Despite the lower S availability, gypsophile species managed to grow without any signs
14 of deficiency and accumulated S to a higher extent than closely-related gypsovags on
15 calcareous soil. We cannot rule out the possibility that S-accumulation is a nutritional
16 requirement of gypsophiles that may impede the completion of their life cycle or their
17 competitive ability in natural conditions. The S content in calcareous soils under greenhouse
18 conditions could be sufficient, but the situation may be different in the field, with lower water
19 availability and increased plant-plant competition. Finally, gypsophiles showed higher leaf S
20 than gypsovags, although some gypsovags also had relatively high leaf S in both soil types.
21 High leaf S concentrations are not exclusive of gypsophiles but also related to phylogenetic
22 effects (Neugebauer *et al.*, 2018). It has been suggested that the ability to accumulate S could
23 be an ancient trait, evolved before the acquisition of gypsophily, that may serve as a pre-
24 requisite to become a gypsophile (Moore *et al.*, 2014).

1 The low leaf K (below 8 mg·g⁻¹) of gypsophiles could be an adaptation to gypseous
2 soils, since low K requirements may be advantageous in soils with low K availability
3 (Alvarado, 1995), such as gypsum (Casby-Horton *et al.*, 2015). Low K requirements are
4 linked to high leaf Ca concentrations in the gypsophile species studied (Alvarado, 1995),
5 since plants have a preference for using Ca ions over other cations such as K, Na or Mg as
6 osmotic compounds (Kinzel, 1989). High leaf Ca has been considered a distinctive trait of
7 gypsophiles (Palacio *et al.*, 2007, Muller *et al.*, 2017), although we did not observe
8 differences between gypsum affinity types. However, gypsophiles showed high leaf Ca
9 concentrations irrespective of the soil type, whereas gypsovags increased Ca concentrations
10 when growing on gypseous soil. This shift can be explained by the higher Ca activity of
11 gypsum as compared to calcareous soils (FAO, 1990). These results seem to indicate a higher
12 ability to uptake Ca in gypsophiles than gypsovags, although further experiments are needed.

13 Gypsophiles species had higher leaf Mg than gypsovags, with increased Mg
14 accumulation on gypsum, where it was highly available. However, neither group of plants
15 shifted Mg concentrations in response to changes in the substrate. Mg accumulation is also a
16 distinctive trait of gypsophile species (Palacio *et al.*, 2007, Merlo *et al.*, 2019). However, Mg
17 concentrations are deeply affected by phylogenetic relationships (White *et al.*, 2018), and
18 some gypsophiles, such as *H. squamatum* and *L. subulatum*, did not show an accumulator
19 pattern, as described by Merlo *et al.* (2019). It has been suggested that high Mg
20 concentrations could be advantageous in gypseous soils, favouring foliar succulence (Merlo *et*
21 *al.*, 2019) or forming crystals with oxalate or sulphate (He *et al.*, 2012) to help detoxify
22 excess S and Ca.

23 Finally, we observed higher leaf Fe, Al, Na, Mn, Cr and Mo concentrations in
24 gypsophiles than gypsovags. Similar to our results, Alvarado *et al.* (1995) found higher leaf

1 Fe and Mn in gypsophiles compared to gypsum soils. Leaf Na was analysed only in few gypsum
2 plant surveys (Bolukbasi *et al.*, 2016, Merlo *et al.*, 2019); where significant differences
3 between gypsum affinities were not observed. Differences in Cr, Mo and Mn between
4 gypsophiles and gypsum soils are difficult to understand, although Mo and Mn are linked to S
5 metabolism (Maillard *et al.*, 2016, Courbet *et al.*, 2019). Despite these general trends, species
6 responded differently to each soil and had different leaf elemental concentration, indicating
7 species-specific responses within gypsum affinities mainly related to S, K and Mg
8 concentrations.

9

10 4.3. Gypseous soils affect the leaf elemental composition of plants

11 Plants grown in gypseous soils had higher leaf S, Mg, Li and lower P and K, mirroring
12 their soil nutrient availability, and also higher Cu and Mn (despite total leaf concentrations
13 that were similar to those in calcareous soils). Thus, gypseous soils affect the leaf elemental
14 composition of plants (Palacio *et al.* 2007, Salmerón-Sánchez *et al.*, 2014), leading mainly to
15 high leaf S and low P regardless of the gypsum affinity of the species (FAO, 1990). Similarly,
16 Boukhris and Lossaint (1970) and Robson *et al.* (2017) observed that plants had high leaf Ca
17 when cultivated on both gypsum and calcareous soil, but less S when growing out of gypsum,
18 according with soil nutrient availability. The mechanisms of P cycling in plants growing on
19 gypsum deserve further study, due to the high relevance of this nutrient for plant growth and
20 the remarkable P immobilization in gypseous soils (FAO, 1990).

21

22 5. Conclusions

23 Gypsophile species grew and were able to complete their life cycle in non-gypseous
24 soils under experimental conditions and in the absence of competition, producing flowers and

1 fruits which rendered viable seeds. Gypsum endemics had similar or higher growth on
2 calcareous than gypseous soil. Most species shifted their leaf elemental composition
3 according to nutrient soil availability, displaying higher leaf S and lower P in gypseous soils.
4 However, gypsophiles accumulated higher S and Mg and lower K concentrations than
5 gypsovags, irrespective of the substrate. The remarkable ability of gypsophiles to accumulate
6 S even in low S-availability conditions suggests a possible nutritional requirement for high S.
7 However, our results indicate this nutritional requirement may not be the unique driver of the
8 exclusion of gypsophiles from non-gypseous soils in natural environments, and the role of
9 other biotic (plant-plant competition, herbivory) and abiotic (water stress) factors deserves
10 further study.

11

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21

22 **Author contributions**

23 GM and SP designed and set up the experiment; AC, maintained the experiment,
24 measured all variables, analysed data and led the manuscript writing; JPF measured and

1 discussed photosynthesis and related traits; All authors discussed the results and wrote the
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3

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10 **Appendices**

11 Appendix A. Supplementary tables

12 Appendix B. Supplementary figures

13

14 **References**

15 Aerts, R., Chapin III, F.S., 1999. The mineral nutrition of wild plants revisited: a re-
16 evaluation of processes and patterns. In *Advances in ecological research*. Academic Press 30,
17 1-67.

18 Aitchison, J., 1982. The statistical analysis of compositional data. *Journal of the Royal*
19 *Statistical Society* 44, 139-160.

20 Alvarado, J.J., 1995. Caracterización del metabolismo mineral de algunas especies de
21 gipsofitos. PhD Thesis, Universidad de Granada, Spain.

22 Artieda, O., Herrero, J., Drohan, P.J., 2006. Refinement of the differential water loss method
23 for gypsum determination in soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal* 70, 1932-1935.

- 1 Ballesteros M, Cañadas EM, Foronda A, Peñas J, Valle F, Lorite J. 2014. Central role of
2 bedding materials for gypsum-quarry restoration: An experimental planting of gypsophile
3 species. *Ecological engineering* 70, 470-476.
- 4 Bates, D., Sarkar, D., Bates, M.D., Matrix, L., 2007. The lme4 package. R package version,
5 2(1), 74.
- 6 Bolukbasi, A., Kurt, L., Palacio, S., 2016. Unravelling the mechanisms for plant survival on
7 gypsum soils: an analysis of the chemical composition of gypsum plants from Turkey. *Plant*
8 *Biology* 18, 271-279.
- 9 Boukhris, M., Lossaint, P., 1975. Aspects ecologiques de la nutrition minerale de plantes
10 gypsicoles de Tunisie. *Revue d'Ecologie et de Biologie du Sol* 12, 329-348.
- 11 Boukhris M, Lossaint P.1970. Sur la teneur en soufre de quelques plantes gypsophiles de
12 Tunisie. *Oecology Plant* 5:345-354.
- 13 Boukhris M, Lossaint P.1972. Spécificité biogéochimique des plantes gypsophiles de Tunisie.
14 *Oecology Plant* 7: 45-68
- 15 Casby-Horton S, Herrero J, Rolong, NA. 2015. Gypsum soils—Their morphology,
16 classification, function, and landscapes. In Sparks D, eds. *Advances in Agronomy*. Academic
17 Press: 231-290
- 18 Comas-Cufí M, Thió-Henestrosa S. 2011. CoDaPack 2.0: a stand-alone, multi-platform
19 compositional software. In: *Egozcue JJ, Tolosana-Delgado R, Ortego MI, eds. CoDaWork'11:*
20 *4th International Workshop on Compositional Data Analysis*. Sant Feliu de Guíxols
- 21 Courbet G, Gallardo K, Vigani G, Brunel-Muguet S, Trouverie J, Salon C, Ourry A. 2019.
22 Disentangling the complexity and diversity of crosstalk between sulfur and other mineral
23 nutrients in cultivated plants. *Journal of Experimental Botany* 70: 4183-4196.

- 1 Duvigneaud P, Denaeyer-De Smet, S. 1968. Essai de classification chimique (éléments
- 2 minéraux) des plantes gypsicoles du bassin de l'Ebre. *Bulletin de la Société Royale de*
- 3 *Botanique de Belgique* 279-291.
- 4 Escudero A, Palacio S, Maestre FT, Luzuriaga, AL. 2014. Plant life on gypsum: a review of
- 5 its multiple facets. *Biological Reviews* 90: 1-18.
- 6 Flowers, TJ, Troke PF, Yeo AR. 1977. The mechanism of salt tolerance in halophytes. *Annual*
- 7 *review of plant physiology* 28: 89-121.
- 8 Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Soil Resources, & Conservation
- 9 Service (FAO).1990. Management of gypseous soils. Rome: Food and Agriculture
- 10 Organization.
- 11 Gankin R, Major J. 1964. *Arctostaphylos myrtifolia*, its biology and relationship to the
- 12 problem of endemism. *Ecology* 45: 792-808.
- 13 He H, Bleby TM, Veneklaas EJ, Lambers H, Kuo J. 2012. Precipitation of calcium,
- 14 magnesium, strontium and barium in tissues of four *Acacia* species (Leguminosae:
- 15 Mimosoideae). *PLoS one* 7: 7 doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0041563
- 16 Herrero J, Porta J. 2000. The terminology and the concepts of gypsum-rich soils. *Geoderma*
- 17 96: 47-61.
- 18 Kalra, Y. 1997. Handbook of reference methods for plant analysis. CRC press.
- 19 Kazakou E, Dimitrakopoulos PG, Baker AJM, Reeves RD, Troumbis AY. 2008. Hypotheses,
- 20 mechanisms and trade-offs of tolerance and adaptation to serpentine soils: from species to
- 21 ecosystem level. *Biological Reviews* 83: 495-508.
- 22 Kinzel H. 1989. Calcium in the vacuoles and cell walls of plant tissue. *Flora* 182: 99-125.
- 23 Kruckeberg AR, Rabinowitz D. 1985. Biological aspects of endemism in higher plants.
- 24 *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics* 16: 447-479.

- 1 Luzuriaga AL, González JM, Escudero, A 2015. Annual plant community assembly in
- 2 edaphically heterogeneous environments. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 26: 866-875.
- 3 Maddison DR, Schulz KS. 2007. The Tree of Life Web Project. Internet address:
- 4 <http://tolweb.org>
- 5 Maillard A, Sorin E, Etienne P, *et al.* 2016. Non-specific root transport of nutrient gives
- 6 access to an early nutritional indicator: The case of sulfate and molybdate. *PloS one* 11: doi:
- 7 10.1371/journal.pone.0166910
- 8 Martinez Arbizu P. 2019. pairwiseAdonis: Pairwise multilevel comparison using adonis. R
- 9 package version 0.3
- 10 Matinzadeh Z, Akhiani H, Abedi M, Palacio S. 2019. The elemental composition of
- 11 halophytes correlates with key morphological adaptations and taxonomic groups. *Plant*
- 12 *Physiology and Biochemistry* 141: 259-278
- 13 McCullagh P, Nelder JA. 1989. Generalized linear models: Monographs on statistics and
- 14 applied probability, 2nd edn. CRC Monographs
- 15 Merlo ME, Garrido-Becerra JA, Mota JF, Salmerón-Sánchez E, Martínez-Hernández F,
- 16 Mendoza-Fernández A, Pérez-García FJ. 2019. Threshold ionic contents for defining the
- 17 nutritional strategies of gypsophile flora. *Ecological indicators* 97: 247-259.
- 18 Meyer SE 1986. The ecology of gypsophile endemism in the eastern Mojave Desert. *Ecology*
- 19 67: 1303-1313.
- 20 Meyer SE. 1980. *The ecology of gypsophily in the eastern Mojave Desert*. PhD Thesis,
- 21 Rancho Santa Ana Botanic Garden, USA
- 22 Montserrat-Marti G, Camarero JJ, Palacio S, Pérez-Rontomé C, Milla R, Albuixech J,
- 23 Maestro M. 2009. Summer-drought constrains the phenology and growth of two coexisting

- 1 Mediterranean oaks with contrasting leaf habit: implications for their persistence and
2 reproduction. *Trees* 23: 787-799.
- 3 Moore MJ, Mota JF, Douglas NA, Flores-Olvera H, Ochoterena H. 2014. The ecology,
4 assembly, and evolution of gypsophile floras. In *Plant Ecology and Evolution in Harsh*
5 *Environments*. Nova Science Publishers, Inc: 97-128
- 6 Mota JF, Garrido-Becerra, JA, Merlo ME, Medina-Cazorla JM, Sánchez-Gómez P. 2017. The
7 edaphism: gypsum, dolomite and serpentine flora and vegetation. In *The Vegetation of the*
8 *Iberian Peninsula*. Springer, Cham: 277-354
- 9 Mota JF, Sánchez-Gómez P, Guirado JS. 2011. Diversidad vegetal de las yeseras ibéricas. *El*
10 *reto de los archipiélagos edáficos para la biología de la conservación*. ADIF-Mediterráneo
11 Asesores Consultores, Almería.
- 12 Muller CT, Moore MJ, Feder Z, Tiley H, Drenovsky RE. 2017. Phylogenetic patterns of foliar
13 mineral nutrient accumulation among gypsophiles and their relatives in the Chihuahuan
14 Desert. *American journal of botany* 104: 1442-1450.
- 15 Munns R, Tester M. 2008. Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annual Review Plant Biology*
16 59: 651-681.
- 17 Neugebauer K, Broadley MR, El-Serehy HA, George TS, McNicol JW, Moraes MF, White
18 PJ. 2018. Variation in the angiosperm ionome. *Physiologia plantarum* 163: 306-322.
- 19 O'Dell RE, James JJ, Richards JH. 2006. Congeneric serpentine and nonserpentine shrubs
20 differ more in leaf Ca: Mg than in tolerance of low N, low P, or heavy metals. *Plant and Soil*
21 280: 49-64.
- 22 Oksanen J, Kindt R, Legendre P, O'Hara B, Stevens MHH, Oksanen MJ, Suggests MASS.
23 2007. The vegan package. *Community ecology package* 10: 631-637.

- 1 Palacio S, Escudero A, Montserrat-Martí G, Maestro M, Milla R, Albert, MJ. 2007. Plants
2 living on gypsum: beyond the specialist model. *Annals of botany* 99: 333-343.
- 3 Palacio S, Hester AJ, Maestro M, Millard P. 2013. Simulated browsing affects leaf shedding
4 phenology and litter quality of oak and birch saplings. *Tree physiology* 33: 438-445.
- 5 Palacio S, Aitkenhead M, Escudero A, Montserrat-Martí G, Maestro M, Robertson AJ. 2014.
6 Gypsophile chemistry unveiled: Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy provides new
7 insight into plant adaptations to gypsum soils. *PLoS One* 9:9
8 doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0107285.
- 9 Palacio S, Montserrat-Martí G, Ferrio JP. 2017. Water use segregation among plants with
10 contrasting root depth and distribution along gypsum hills. *Journal of vegetation science* 28:
11 1107-1117.
- 12 Pérez-Harguindeguy N, Díaz S, Garnier E, *et al.* 2013. New handbook for standardised
13 measurement of plant functional traits worldwide. *Australian Journal of Botany* 61: 167-234.
- 14 Prater C, Scott DE, Lance SL, Nunziata SO, Sherman R, Tomczyk N, Capps KA, Jeyasingh
15 PD. 2019. Understanding variation in salamander ionomes: A nutrient balance approach.
16 *Freshwater biology* 64: 294-305.
- 17 Robson T, Stevens J, Dixon K, Reid N. 2017. Sulfur accumulation in gypsum-forming
18 thiophores has its roots firmly in calcium. *Environmental and Experimental Botany* 137: 208-
19 219.
- 20 Quirantes J. 1978. Estudio sedimentológico y estratigráfico del Terciario continental de
21 los Monegros. Instituto Fernando El Católico CSIC Diputación Provincial, Zaragoza.
- 22 R Core Team. 2020. *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation
23 for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.

- 1 Rorison IH. 1960. Some experimental aspects of the calcicole-calcifuge problem: I. The
2 effects of competition and mineral nutrition upon seedling growth in the field. *The Journal of*
3 *Ecology* 48: 585-599.
- 4 Salmerón-Sánchez E, Martínez-Nieto MI, Martínez-Hernández F, Garrido-Becerra JA, Mendoza-
5 Fernández AJ, de Carrasco CG, Mota JF. 2014. Ecology, genetic diversity and phylogeography of the
6 Iberian endemic plant *Jurinea pinnata* (Lag.) DC.(Compositae) on two special edaphic substrates:
7 dolomite and gypsum. *Plant and Soil* 374: 233-250.
- 8 Soriano-Disla JM, Janik L, McLaughlin MJ, Forrester S, Kirby J, Reimann C, The
9 EuroGeoSurveys GEMAS Project Team. 2013. The use of diffuse reflectance mid-infrared
10 spectroscopy for the prediction of the concentration of chemical elements estimated by X-ray
11 fluorescence in agricultural and grazing European soils. *Applied geochemistry* 29: 135-143.
- 12 Stout PR, Meagher WR, Pearson GA, Johnson CM 1951. Molybdenum nutrition of crop
13 plants: I. The influence of phosphate and sulfate on the absorption of molybdenum from soils
14 and solution cultures. *Plant and Soil* 51-87.
- 15 Wenk EH, Dawson TE. 2007. Interspecific differences in seed germination, establishment,
16 and early growth in relation to preferred soil type in an alpine community. *Arctic, Antarctic,*
17 *and Alpine Research* 39: 165-176.
- 18 Wickham H. 2016. ggplot2. In: *Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag New
19 York. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>.
- 20 White PJ, Broadley MR, El-Serehy HA, George TS, Neugebauer K. 2018. Linear
21 relationships between shoot magnesium and calcium concentrations among angiosperm
22 species are associated with cell wall chemistry. *Annals of botany* 122: 221-226.

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24
25

1 TABLES

2 Table 1: Characteristics of study species

Species	Family	Gypsum affinity	Gypsophily*	Seed collection (Spain)
<i>Boleum asperum</i> Desv.	Brassicaceae	Gypsovag	3.03	Castelflorite
<i>Gypsophila struthium</i> subsp. <i>hispanica</i> (Willk.) G.López	Caryophyllaceae	Gypsophile	4.69	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Helianthemum squamatum</i> Pers.	Cistaceae	Gypsophile	4.87	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Helianthemum syriacum</i> (Jacq.) Dum.Cours.	Cistaceae	Gypsovag	-	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Herniaria fruticosa</i> L.	Caryophyllaceae	Gypsophile	4.05	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Lepidium subulatum</i> L.	Brassicaceae	Gypsophile	4.91	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Linum suffruticosum</i> DC.	Linaceae	Gypsovag	-	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Matthiola fruticulosa</i> (L.) Maire	Brassicaceae	Gypsovag	-	Sariñena
<i>Ononis tridentata</i> L.	Fabaceae	Gypsophile	4.43	Villamayor de Gállego
<i>Salvia officinalis</i> Spenn.	Lamiaceae	Gypsovag	-	Leciñena

3 *Exclusivity to gypseous soils in Spain from expert evaluation. Values of gypsophily range between 0 and 5. Extracted from Mota *et al.*,
 4 (2011)

5

6

1 Table 2: Means and standard deviation of leaf traits, seed traits, growth and phenological
 2 variables for each treatment. Major letters indicate significant differences between
 3 gypsophiles and gypsovags regardless of the soil type ($P < 0.05$). Minor letters indicate
 4 significant differences between soil types ($P < 0.05$) within each gypsum affinity group.

Variables	Gypsovags				Gypsophiles			
	Calcareous		Gypseous		Calcareous		Gypseous	
Final canopy area (dm ²)	10.71±7.30	A	8.73±4.57	A	18.42±11.03	Ba	15.27±9.42	Bb
Final length (mm)	189.28±64.37		200.17±68.29		176.24±88.65		165.71±76.22	
Gradualness	19.58±12.52		20.06±12.92		20.52±12.62		21.04±13.36	
Max. shoot growth rate (mm·day ⁻¹)	1.21±0.99		1.12±1.34		1.27±1.40		1.02±0.95	
Day max. shoot growth rate	372.44±49.63	A	388.54±63.54	A	425.40±44.03	Ba	398.04±56.15	Bb
E (mmol H ₂ O m ⁻² s ⁻¹)	5.77±2.37		6.12±3.33		8.07±3.56		6.47±4.08	
A (μmol CO ₂ ·m ⁻² ·s ⁻¹)	12.01±1.94		10.01±3.18		12.87±5.49		9.69±4.19	
Gs (mmol·m ⁻² ·s ⁻¹)	507.31±292.08		563.49±375.79		599.43±362.60		475.69±313.17	
WUE	2.34±0.82		2.00±0.94		1.82±0.91		2.09±1.61	
SLA(cm ² /g)	63.36±33.78		55.02±20.81		84.63±45.46	a	66.46±38.28	b
LDMC (mg·g ⁻¹)	280.99±97.34	A	297.42±78.36	A	197.87±83.18	B	194.57±69.59	B
Leaf N (%)	1.72±0.98	a	1.66±0.87	b	1.56±0.97		1.59±0.84	
Day 1st Flower	340.25±30.25	Aa	360.18±28.80	Ab	402.40±41.83	B	411.80±32.05	B
Day Max Flowering	363.63±23.08	A	373.59±25.60	A	421.73±42.99	B	428.80±36.60	B
Max. Flowering (% stems)	63.13±27.68	A	68.82±17.64	A	42.00±26.17	B	29.33±23.74	B
Individual seed mass (mg)	0.77±0.73	a	0.91±0.62	b	1.38±2.19		2.83±3.33	
Total biomass (g)	12.85±11.96	a	9.40±6.39	b	13.13±10.52		12.54±9.40	
Root:Shoot	1.66±0.62	A	1.54±0.69	A	1.12±0.44	B	1.21±0.51	B

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- 1 Table 3: F-ratios, P-value and Variability ($SS_{\text{factor}}/SS_{\text{total}}$) from non-parametric contrasts based
- 2 on distances in which soil ($a = 2$), gypsum affinity types ($b = 2$) and species ($c = 10$) were
- 3 fixed factors. Data set of $N=180$.

Leaf elemental composition	Treatments				
	Soil	Gypsum affinity	Species	Soil*Gypsum affinity	Soil*Species
F-ratio	25.55	90.59	42.47	0.58	1.71
P-value	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.732	0.013
Variability (%)	4.04	14.33	53.75	0.09	2.17

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5

- 1 Table 4: Means and standard deviation of leaf elemental concentration ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) for each
- 2 treatment. Major letters indicate significant differences between gypsophiles and gypsovags
- 3 regardless of the soil type ($P < 0.05$) Minor letters indicate significant differences between
- 4 soil types ($P < 0.05$) within each gypsum affinity group.

Element ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	Gypsovags				Gypsophiles			
	Calcareous		Gypseous		Calcareous		Gypseous	
Al	0.3±0.1	A	0.3±0.1	A	0.5±0.6	B	0.4±0.4	B
C	429.0±47.7		427.7±47.7		389.7±47.7	a	378.8±56.7	b
Ca	26.4±12.3	a	30.3±14.1	b	46.9±22.4		46.0±21.8	
Cr	1.3E-2±1.1E-2	A	1.5E-2±1.7E-2	A	3.4E-2±7.3E-2	Ba	2.4E-2±4.7E-2	Bb
Cu	1.0E-2±6.1E-3		1.2E-2±9.4E-3		1.2E-2±6.7E-3	a	1.3E-2±5.6E-3	b
Fe	0.3±0.1	A	0.3±0.1	A	0.5±0.7	B	0.4±0.5	B
K	10.4±3.2	Aa	8.3±3.3	Ab	8.2±4.1	Ba	6.2±2.3	Bb
Li	4.5E-3±4.5E-3	a	6.8E-3±7.3E-3	b	3.6E-3±3.0E-3	a	5.4E-3±5.5E-3	b
Mg	4.1±2.1	A	4.1±2.0	A	8.8±5.3	B	10.8±7.4	B
Mn	6.2E-2±2.8E-2	A	5.7E-2±2.8E-2	A	7.8E-2±2.8E-2	Ba	6.4E-2±2.2E-2	Bb
Mo	5.6E-3±5.6E-3		7.8E-3±7.7E-3		6.1E-3±4.4E-3	a	1.7E-2±2.0E-2	b
N	17.3±8.8		15.9±8.9		15.3±8.1		14.5±7.4	
Na	1.0E-1±6.5E-2	A	8.7E-2±3.0E-2	A	1.4E-1±6.1E-2	B	1.3E-1±6.1E-2	B
P	2.3±1.5	a	1.1±0.6	b	2.4±2.6	a	1.0±0.7	b
S	5.9±4.2	Aa	7.7±4.7	Ab	15.6±7.6	Ba	24.4±16.4	Bb
Si	1.0±0.2		1.0±0.2		1.0±0.3		1.0±0.3	
Ti	3.7E-3±1.3E-3		4.2E-3±2.1E-3		5.6E-3±5.8E-3		5.5E-3±5.6E-3	
Zn	5.1E-2±3.2E-2		5.3E-2±2.9E-2		5.1E-2±4.9E-2		5.0E-2±3.8E-2	

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1 FIGURE CAPTIONS

2 Figure 1: A) Variation in relative shoot growth (mm/mm day⁻¹) and B) percentage of
3 flowering stems (%) from December 2017 to September 2018. Centroids of each treatment
4 mean were drawn (\pm S.E.). Circles indicate gypsophiles; squares, gypsovags. Filled symbols
5 indicate plants grown on gypsiferous soils; empty symbols, calcareous soils

6

7 Figure 2: Biplot distance of first and second principal components based on Center Log-ratio
8 transformation of leaf elemental composition. Centroids of each treatment mean were drawn
9 (\pm S.D.). Circles indicate gypsophiles; squares, gypsovags. Filled symbols indicate plants
10 grown on gypsiferous soils; empty symbols, calcareous soils. BoAs: *B.asperum*; GyHi:
11 *G.hispanica*; HeFr: *H.fruticosa*; HeSq: *H.squamatum*; HeSy: *H.syriacum*; LeSu: *L.subulatum*;
12 LiSu: *L.suffruticosum*; MaFr: *M.fruticulosa*; OnTr: *Ononis tridentata*; RoOf: *R.officinalis*;
13 WA: all gypsophiles on calcareous soils; VA: all gypsovags on calcareous soils; WY: all
14 gypsophiles on gypsiferous soils; VY: all gypsovags on gypsiferous soils.

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1 SUPPLEMENTARY CAPTIONS

2 Table A.1: Means and standard deviation of physicochemical features of native soils.

3

4 Table A.2: Means and standard deviation of elemental composition of native soils.

5

6 Table A.3: F-ratios of GLMMs in which soil (calcareous and gypseous) and gypsum affinity
7 (gypsovag and gypsophile) were fixed factors and species was a random factor. Bold type
8 indicates $P < 0.05$.

9

10 Table A.4: F-ratios of GLMMs within gypsum affinities in which soil (calcareous and
11 gypseous) was a fixed factor and species was a random factor. Bold type indicates $P < 0.05$.

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13 Table A.5: F-ratios of GLMMs with soil (calcareous and gypseous) and gypsum affinity
14 (gypsovag and gypsophile) as fixed factors and time, family and species nested within family
15 as random factors. Bold type indicates $P < 0.05$.

16

17 Table A.6: F-ratios of GLMMs within gypsum affinity types in which soil (calcareous and
18 gypseous) was a fixed factors and time, family and species nested within family were random
19 factors. Bold type indicates $P < 0.05$.

20

21 Table A.7: Means and standard deviation of the Euclidean distance between the chemical
22 composition of each species in gypseous vs. calcareous soil, plus differences between soil
23 types on each species based on Center Log-ratio transformed elements. F-ratios. P-value from

1 multiple comparisons of species*soil interaction. P-values were adjusted by Bonferroni. Bold
2 type indicates the three most variable elements on each species between soil types.

3

4 Table A.8: F-ratios of GLMM within species in which soil (calcareous and gypseous) was a
5 fixed factor and time was a random factor (b=2). Bold type indicates $P < 0.05$.

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7 Table A.9: Means and standard deviation of elemental concentrations of study species grown
8 on calcareous and gypseous soil.

9

10 Figure B.1: Biplot distance of second and third principal components based on Center Log-
11 Ratio transformed elements. Centroids of each treatment mean were drawn (\pm S.D.). Circles
12 indicate gypsophiles; squares, gypsovags. Filled symbols indicate plants grown on
13 gypsiferous soils; empty symbols, calcareous soils. BoAs: *B.asperum*; GyHi: *G.hispanica*;
14 HeFr: *H.fruticosa*; HeSq: *H.squamatum*; HeSy: *H.syriacum*; LeSu: *L.subulatum*; LiSu:
15 *L.suffruticosum*; MaFr: *M.fruticulosa*; OnTr: *Ononis tridentata*; RoOf: *R.officinalis*; WA: all
16 gypsophiles on calcareous soils; VA: all gypsovags on calcareous soils; WY: all gypsophiles
17 on gypsiferous soils; VY: all gypsovags on gypsiferous soils.

18

19 Figure B.2: Biplot distance of first and second redundancy components based on Center Log-
20 Ratio transformed elements. Centroids of each treatment mean were drawn (\pm S.D.). Circles
21 indicate gypsophiles; squares, gypsovags. Filled symbols indicate plants grown on
22 gypsiferous soils; empty symbols, calcareous soils. BoAs: *B.asperum*; GyHi: *G.hispanica*;
23 HeFr: *H.fruticosa*; HeSq: *H.squamatum*; HeSy: *H.syriacum*; LeSu: *L.subulatum*; LiSu:
24 *L.suffruticosum*; MaFr: *M.fruticulosa*; OnTr: *Ononis tridentata*; RoOf: *R.officinalis*; WA: all

1 gypsophiles on calcareous soils; VA: all gypsovags on calcareous soils; WY: all gypsophiles
2 on gypsiferous soils; VY: all gypsovags on gypsiferous soils.

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4 Figure B.3: HeatMap of Euclidean distance based on Center Log-ratio transformed foliar
5 concentrations of elements. Centroids of each treatment mean were drawn. Greyer colours
6 indicate furthest and whitish grey shows plants with more similar leaf elemental composition.

7 BoAs: *B. asperum*; GyHi: *G. hispanica*; HeFr: *H. fruticosa*; HeSq: *H. squamatum*; HeSy:

8 *H. syriacum*; LeSu: *L. subulatum*; LiSu: *L. suffruticosum*; MaFr: *M. fruticulosa*; OnTr: *Ononis*

9 *tridentata*; RoOf: *R. officinalis*; Calc: on calcareous soils; Gyp: on gypsiferous soils. Species

10 with asterisk are gypsophiles. The cladogram is an adapted phylogenetic tree.

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